

EPIDEMIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF HEPATITIS B SCREENING INDICATORS IN URGENCH

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Abstract.

The current research evaluates the outcomes of hepatitis B virus screening conducted in Urgench between 2023 and 2025. The aim of the study was to assess detection rates of the disease. Epidemiological, statistical, serological, and PCR methods were used. According to the findings, out of 25,840 individuals examined, 0.68% tested positive for the HBV markers, with the highest prevalence observed in the 31–45 age group. The findings highlight the need to improve regional epidemiological surveillance and strengthen targeted screening among high-risk populations.

Keywords: hepatitis B, screening, epidemiological, statistical, serological, PCR.

Relevance.

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is a global infectious disease that can lead to chronic liver damage, cirrhosis, and hepatocellular carcinoma. According to the 2024 report of the World Health Organization (WHO), 254 million people worldwide are living with chronic hepatitis B infection, and approximately 1.2 million new cases are reported annually. [3,4] In 2022, 1.1 million deaths were attributed to hepatitis B, primarily due to liver cirrhosis and hepatocellular carcinoma (the primary type of liver cancer). [3] WHO has set a goal to eliminate hepatitis by 2030 and recommends strengthening screening, vaccination, and treatment strategies. [1]

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the prevalence of hepatitis B infection is considered moderately high, with increased risk particularly in maternity hospitals, hemodialysis centers, and blood transfusion units. Currently, in order to enhance the prevention of all viral hepatitis types and to ensure early detection among the population, large-scale measures are being implemented in accordance with the Resolution No. PQ-243 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 16, 2022, “On Further Improvement of Measures to Reduce the Incidence and Prevent Viral Hepatitis.” Taking Urgench city as an example, an increase in the virus detection rate has been observed as a result of mass screening programs conducted between 2023 and 2025. Specifically, the prevalence of the disease among the socio-economically active population necessitates further improvement of regional epidemiological surveillance and a comprehensive analysis of diagnostic methods, including serological and PCR testing. [6] The aim of this study was to analyze Hepatitis B screening results in Urgench city during 2023–2025 and evaluate detection rates.

Materials and Methods.

This study employed epidemiological (retrospective), statistical (Fisher’s exact test), and serological (rapid diagnostic test) approaches. At the confirmatory stage, molecular genetic analysis was performed using polymerase chain reaction (PCR). The study utilized official data on Hepatitis B screening obtained from the Urgench City Department of the Committee for Sanitary and Epidemiological Welfare and Public Health.

Results. A retrospective analysis conducted among the population of Urgench city revealed that a total of 25,840 individuals were screened for HBV during the period 2023–2025, of whom 0.68% were confirmed to be positive for the virus.

In 2023, a total of 10,830 individuals underwent screening, representing the highest coverage within the study period. Analysis of the interim data for 2025 indicates that, despite a lower screening

coverage of 7,810 individuals, an upward trend in the number of detected cases was observed compared to earlier periods (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Percentage (%) distribution of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) positive cases by year in Urgench city, 2023–2025.

When analyzed by year, 2023 accounted for 35.8% of cases, while 2024 represented 6.3%. The highest proportion was observed in 2025, which accounted for 57.9% of all cases. These findings indicate that, despite a lower number of screenings in 2025 compared to 2023, the efficiency of case detection increased markedly. This trend may be explained by improved diagnostic accuracy or an expanded coverage of targeted screening among high-risk groups.

The overall analysis of all Hepatitis B virus (HBV)-positive cases identified during the study by age groups indicates that the infection predominantly affects the socioeconomically active segment of the population. According to the obtained data, more than half of all positive cases (51.1%) were observed in the 31–45 age group. This finding suggests that this age group represents a high-risk population for Hepatitis B virus infection, thereby logically justifying the need to focus preventive measures specifically on this cohort to enhance their effectiveness (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Distribution of all identified HBV cases (n = 176) by age groups.

The next highest proportion of disease burden was observed in the 46–60 age group, accounting for 28.9%. Further distribution across age groups showed 11.9% in the 18–30 age group, while the lowest proportion was recorded among individuals aged over 60 years (8.1%). Overall, these findings provide an objective assessment of the epidemiological situation of Hepatitis B virus infection in the studied area and confirm the importance of age as a key factor in defining strategies for disease control and prevention.

The analysis of the gender distribution of identified HBV cases revealed an almost equal prevalence between males and females. Of the total patients, 51.1% (n = 90) were male and 48.9% (n = 86) were female. This finding indicates that the virus is distributed in the studied area without significant gender-related differences.

Conclusions:

When analyzing the dynamics of Hepatitis B virus (HBV) detection in Urgench city over the period 2023–2025, a total of 176 positive cases were recorded during the study period. The highest detection rate was observed in 2025, accounting for 57.9% of all cases. This increase is directly associated with the expansion of screening activities covering 7,810 individuals during that period, as well as improved laboratory diagnostic quality, which facilitated the active identification of previously undetected epidemiological foci.

The analysis of the gender distribution of identified HBV cases revealed that the virus was disseminated in the study area without a clear gender-based difference. Of the total patients, 51.1% (n = 90) were male and 48.9% (n = 86) were female, indicating an almost equal distribution between the two groups.

The analysis of the age distribution of patients confirmed that the infection predominantly affects the socioeconomically active segment of the population. The highest incidence was recorded in the 31–45 age group, accounting for more than half of all positive cases (51.1%). The subsequent distribution across age groups showed 28.9% in the 46–60 age group, 11.9% in the 18–30 age group, and the lowest proportion among individuals aged over 60 years (8.1%).

The obtained results provide an epidemiological basis for further improving preventive measures against Hepatitis B virus infection in Urgench city, as well as for continuing targeted diagnostic activities among high-risk groups, particularly the 31–45 age cohort.

ADABIYOTLAR RO'YHATI:

1. World Health Organization. Global health sector strategies on HIV, viral hepatitis and sexually transmitted infections for the period 2022–2030. Geneva: WHO; 2022. <https://www.cdc.gov/mmwr/volumes/70/wr/mm7030a1.htm>
2. World Health Organization. Global hepatitis report 2024. Geneva: WHO; 2024.
3. World Health Organization. Hepatitis B fact sheet. Updated 2024. Geneva: WHO.
4. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Sog'liqni saqlash vazirligi. Virusli gepatitlar bo'yicha milliy ma'lumotlar. <https://gov.uz/oz/ssv>
5. Polaris Observatory Collaborators. Global prevalence, treatment, and prevention of hepatitis B virus infection in 2023: a modelling study. *Lancet Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2023.
6. Schweitzer A, Horn J, Mikolajczyk RT, Krause G, Ott JJ. Estimations of worldwide prevalence of chronic hepatitis B virus infection: a systematic review of data published between 2015 and 2022. *Lancet*. 2023 update.
7. Abakay S, Döngelli H, Daniş N, et al. Prevalence and screening rates of hepatitis B virus infection. *Trop Med Infect Dis*. 2025;10(9):258.
8. Terrault NA, Lok ASF, McMahon BJ, et al. Update on prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of chronic hepatitis B. *Hepatology*. 2023.
9. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Viral Hepatitis Surveillance Report United States, 2023. Atlanta: CDC; 2024.

10. European Association for the Study of the Liver (EASL). EASL clinical practice guidelines on hepatitis B. J Hepatol. 2023 update.
11. Terrault NA, Lok ASF, McMahon BJ, et al. Update on prevention, diagnosis, and treatment of chronic hepatitis B: AASLD 2023 guidance. Hepatology. 2023.